

Raising Awareness of the Clothing Trends for People with Intellectual Disabilities

Ilham Fathy Abdel Aziz

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Abstract

The study aims to prepare a proposed program to develop the dressing trends of children with intellectual disabilities in the simple and medium disability category and to arrive at a rehabilitation program to develop awareness of clothing trends, through which they can acquire daily life skills related to clothes (design - color - material), and the current study seeks to verify the following hypotheses: There is a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the experimental group scores in the pre-measurement and the post-measurement scale for developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills associated with clothing (design) in favor of post-measurement. There is a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the experimental group scores in the pre/post score of the Scale for developing awareness of clothing trends and daily living skills related to clothing (color) in favor of the post measurement. There is a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the experimental group scores in the pre/post score of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (material) in favor of post-measurement. There is a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the experimental group scores in the pre-measurement and the post-measurement scale for developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills associated with clothing (the scale as a whole) in favor of post-measurement. There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the experimental group and the control group in the dimensional measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (design) for the benefit of the experimental group. There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the experimental and control group in the dimensional measurement of the scale of developing awareness of attitudes of clothing and daily life skills associated with clothing (color) in favor of the experimental group. There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the experimental and control group in the dimensional measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (material) in favor of the experimental group. There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the experimental and control group in the dimensional measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (the scale as a whole) in favor of the experimental group. The importance of the study is represented in finding a program in the field of intellectual disability to help children with mild and moderate intellectual disabilities " Those who are able to learn about psychological and social compatibility by providing them with daily life skills, and it can also be used in developing curricula for children with intellectual disabilities" .The study used the experimental approach based on the two groups "control and experimental" on a sample of (20 children) of children with intellectual disability. The results showed the effect of the program's effectiveness and the development of clothing trends among children with mild intellectual disabilities, and that any intervention in improving the educational environment for the intellectually disabled child, and the use of standardized educational techniques, activities, and programs for intellectually disabled children, "simple and medium-disabled", can improve their abilities. And then raising the public taste.

Introduction

Clothes reflect the individual's idea of himself and his personality, as it is considered a means of aesthetic and artistic expression and a reflection of the personal feeling of artistic components and is evident in what the individual chooses of clothes, and his ability to interact with aesthetic values in things and form a sound aesthetic judgment, with the aim of awakening the individual's sense to become aware of the aesthetic aspect around him (Samah 2016).

Clothes are among the blessings of God upon man, so God counted them and mentioned them in the Holy Quran, that is why God Almighty said we are grateful for His servants with this blessing (*O Children of Adam! We have bestowed raiment upon you to cover yourselves (screen your private parts) and as an adornment; and the raiment of righteousness, that is better. Such are among the Ayât (proofs, evidence, verses, lessons, signs, revelations, etc.) of Allâh, that they may remember (i.e. leave falsehood and follow truth).* Surat Al-A'raf: verse 26.

A person should enjoy wisdom and logic, and think about the image he wants to reflect on himself and leave it in the minds of others about him, as the way we choose clothes tells others many things about us, and a person must ask himself where he will go, about the people he will meet, and then decide what clothes, materials and colors are appropriate (Bartara, g, 2002: 34), rather, the emphasis is on spreading the clothing awareness of the individual and society by highlighting the aesthetic and utilitarian values of clothes within the framework of customs and traditions. (Frey Colon, 2000: 95).

With the increasing global interest in persons with intellectual disabilities, as the percentage of people with special needs in the Arab world ranges between 0.4% -4.9% of the total population (Mosaada, 2016) and qualify them and work to benefit from their limited energies and capabilities in order to achieve adaptation to the environment and prepare them to integrate into the society in which they live.

And by declaring global bodies concerned with the affairs of persons with disabilities such as: American Association of Intellectual Impairment, and the National Association of Intellectual Impotence in the United Kingdom, training and rehabilitation is a fundamental right of persons with intellectual disabilities by society, it also stressed the need to prepare and implement the programs necessary to qualify them for social life and prepare them to depend on themselves in carrying out their daily affairs to the extent that their remaining potentials and capabilities allow.

Researchers in the field of intellectual disability have emphasized the importance of children with intellectual disabilities acquiring daily living skills (Evelyn H. Kroesbergen, Johannes E.H. Van Luit, 2003). As these children are characterized by their inability to practice aspects of daily life due to their limitations in their intellectual abilities, which requires training them in a range of skills related to daily life. Such as eating and drinking skills, dressing and hygiene skills, as well as social skills. And since the acquisition of daily skills is learned by a non-disabled child during his stay in the family group in a normal and easy way, but it is not as easy as for a child with an intellectual disability, therefore, the family finds it a burden and difficulty in teaching its child those skills that greatly help him to be independent and take care of himself. Hence the need and urgent to care for this group in a special way that differs from that provided to children without disabilities. And that is through a qualifying program to develop awareness of clothing trends through which they can acquire daily life skills related to clothes (design - color - material).

Research problem

The research problem can be formulated in the following questions:

1. What is the possibility of preparing a program to develop the dressing trends of children with intellectual disabilities?
2. How effective is the proposed program for developing attitudes of clothing among children with intellectual disabilities?

Research hypotheses

- There is a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the experimental group scores in the pre- and post-measurement of the Scale for Developing Awareness of Clothing Trends and Daily Living Skills related to clothing (design) in favor of post-measurement.

- There is a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the experimental group scores in the pre/ post score on the scale for developing awareness of attitudes of clothing and daily life skills related to clothing (color) in favor of post measurement.

- There is a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the experimental group scores in the pre/ post score on the scale for developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to (material) clothing in favor of post-measurement.

- There is a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the experimental group scores in the pre-measurement and the post-measurement scale for developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills associated with clothing (the scale as a whole) in favor of post-measurement.

- There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the experimental group and the control group in the post-measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (design) for the benefit of the experimental group.

- There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the experimental group and the control group in the post-measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (color) in favor of the experimental group.

- There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the experimental and control group in the post-measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (material) in favor of the experimental group.

- There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the experimental and control group in the post-measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (the scale as a whole) in favor of the experimental group.

Research objectives

1. Preparing a proposed program for developing the attitudes of clothing for children with an intellectual disability in the category of simple disability.

2. Verify knowledge of the impact of working with groups programs on children with intellectual disabilities, who have simple disabilities, to equip them with daily living skills.

3. Finding a program in the field of intellectual disability to help the intellectually disabled child achieve psychological and social compatibility by providing him with daily living skills.

Research importance

1. Contributes to the possibility of using modern technology, and making use of it in the preparation of educational and training programs provided to children.

2. Benefiting from the proposed program in the research to develop the attitudes of clothing among children, and then raising the public taste.

3. Opening the door to creating a positive and effective role for children by recognizing the proper dressing trends and providing them with the ability to have confidence and self-reliance.

4. Enriching the Arab library in the field of caring for people with special needs.

Research terms

Intellectual disability:

The American Society for Intellectual Disability (now known as the American Association for Intellectual and Developmental Disabilities) defined intellectual disability as: A condition that indicates concrete deficiencies in the current job performance of an individual, and the condition is characterized by clearly below average intellectual performance that is associated with related deficiencies in two or more of the following adaptive skills areas:

Communication, self-care, home life, social skills, use of societal resources, self-orientation, healthy habits, safety and security, academic skills, work and leisure skill, and intellectual disability appears before the age of eighteen. (Yousef Al-Qaryouti, Abdulaziz Al-Sartawi and Jamil Al-Smadi, 2001: 57).

Clothing awareness

The awareness of clothing means the provision of information, skills and experiences through the clear integrated concept of many aspects of the educational process related to the art of dress, and learn about the importance of clothes for the individual, their types inside and outside the home, and the methods of choosing clothes. (Amal Al-Fayoumi, Al-Youssef, 2007).

Research limits

Spatial limits: Abjad Center for Special Care in Jeddah

Time limits: The study was conducted in 2020 AD - 1441 AH

Previous studies

The previous studies dealt with methods of life experiences and their role in developing various concepts such as the study of Amal Hassan (2013), which aimed to investigate the extent to which the supermarket is activated to develop some concepts and life-mathematical skills in a kindergarten child, as well as knowing the extent of the kindergarten child's ability to acquire life mathematical skills during his interaction in all the operations that take place within the supermarket (selling, buying, organizing goods on shelves, methods of displaying goods) where agreed with the results of Marwa Suleiman's study (2007), which searched for a program to impart some mathematical concepts among ordinary kindergarten children and the hearing impaired and that is through programs to develop their mathematical concepts and based on the importance of activities in the lives of ordinary kindergarten children and the hearing-impaired. Through various activities, the personalities of these children can be built, and they can learn indirectly.

Abeer Mahmoud (2012) also emphasized the effectiveness of a proposed program based on the concept of integration in developing techniques for hand-printing and achievement in mathematics among mentally disabled students who are able to learn, the studies related to the preparation and design of educational units and programs in Art Education and Special Education and studies that rely on the use of the integration approach in the fields of education and which are concerned with the elements and foundations of design include printing and the field of manual printing. The study also dealt with the characteristics of the mentally disabled, the methods of rehabilitation and care for them, as well as their individual characteristics, general characteristics of their growth, the role of the art education teacher, and the characteristics of the arts of mentally retarded children. The performance methods for handprinting, prints, templates, tools, materials, printing steps, advantages and disadvantages.

As for Christine Kristen's (2007) study, it focused on mathematical skills in children with Down syndrome, and these skills were tested through the Test of Early Mathematical Abilities (TEMA-z). And it is a test that measures a wide number of skills such as verbal abilities and numerical streak. The sample was 28 children, 14 of whom were children with Down syndrome, and 14 of them were normal children (males and females). The results found that there were differences in the responses of the two groups, but the responses of children with Down syndrome were more than expected. In addition, it was proven that the children's ability to read numbers is very high, and it may reach the level of a normal child, which indicates that verbal math skills may be stronger in these children than written mathematical skills. And on the relationship of merging the mentally retarded category with the normal ones while learning some different concepts and solving problems, it was revealed from the study of Bottge, Brian A. ; Ma, Xin; Gassaway, Linda; Toland, Michael D. ; Butler, Mark; Cho, Sun-Joo (2014). That the mentally retarded children combined with normal children had acquired mathematical concepts related to proportions and geometry.

The study by Evelyn H. Kroesbergen, Johannes E.H. Van Luit (2003) emphasized the importance of using problem-solving strategy to teach basic principles and skills of mathematics to people with special needs, the results also showed the importance of learning duration and the necessity of teaching them through self-learning as the most effective method, and also emphasized the role of computers while learning basic mathematics skills.

As for (Elia, Iliada; Evangelou, Kyriacoulla (2014) study, it emphasized the importance of the role of non-verbal gestures in learning spatial concepts in children, and it is a study focused on the role of verbal and non-verbal behavior in learning spatial concepts "in - outside - inside - under - up - down" by using non-verbal gestures that help to understand spatial relationships that were abstract for the child and were not sufficiently represented by verbal or oral expression.

Ola Youssef and Hoda Sultan (2006) study emphasized the importance of female students' awareness of the environmental dimension of their clothes. The study concluded: - Decreased awareness of students of the effect of the type of material, design, and equipment on individual health, and decreased awareness of the importance of the presence of the advisory card and their lack of awareness of some of its items.

The study of Zainab Muhammad and GilanJuma (2011) emphasized the necessity of contributing to the achievement of the style of clothing and the ability to choose the right textile, and introducing modern concepts and trends in textile and clothing.

The Study Methodology

Procedural steps for research

Research Methodology:

This research followed the experimental method in addition to the applied study for its suitability to achieve the objectives of the research and verify its hypotheses.

The research sample

The research sample consists of 20 girls enrolled in the Abjad Center for Special Care, and their disabilities range from low to medium and the intellectual age ranges between 6 and 9 years old and the IQ ranges between 50 and 70.

The sample is divided into two groups: The control group is (10) children, and education and training are carried out according to the educational program followed by the center, and an experimental group: They are (10) children, and education and training are carried out using the proposed program and applying all activities.

Table 1: The homogeneity between the control and experimental groups in intelligence

Variable	Group	Average ranks	Total ranks	Manuitney	Critical ratio	Indication
Intelligence	Control	10	94.8	8500.2	317.0-	Not

Experimental	10	6.8	statistically
Total	20		significant

Research tools:

- Questionnaire for studying attitudes of clothing for children with intellectual disability (pre) and (post).

- The rehabilitation program for girls with intellectual disabilities to develop dress awareness.

First: Validity and reliability of the questionnaire

Validation of the questionnaire:

The validity of the arbitrators:

- And that was through 9 arbitrators specialized in education, curricula, teaching methods, and psychology in the field of education and disability, and the percentage of agreement among them was 00.96%.

- The validity was calculated by the internal consistency validity method, which is the correlation coefficient between each dimension of the scale and the total score. The researcher also calculated the validity of the purpose of the test by finding the correlation coefficient between the degree of each of the test dimensions and the total score, which is shown in the following table:

Table 2: The validity of the test using the correlation coefficient between the degree of each of the test dimensions and the overall score

Dimension	Correlation coefficient
Design	** 716.0
Material	** 718.0
Color	** 816.0

** Significant at the level of significance (0.01) The value of the tabular correlation coefficient at the level of (0.01) = 0.561.

Questionnaire Reliability

The reliability of the scale was calculated by two methods: (re-test - mid-segmentation).

- As for the Test - retest method, the scale is re-applied with an interval of two weeks, and the correlation coefficient reached (0,885), and the reliability coefficient (0,866).

- The reliability of the previous rationing sample was calculated by another method, which is the mid-segmentation method and its value was (874.0), using Pearson's coefficient.

The special qualification program for girls with intellectual disabilities to develop dress awareness:

Children with intellectual disability (Mental Retardation Mild), just like normal children, go through the same different stages of development, but slowly, and therefore, it is necessary to know which of these stages there is failure of the child to help him pass it successfully according to his abilities and capabilities, to move him to another stage, higher in the class, to suit his age as best he can. Therefore, it is important to present different and varied programs that meet the needs of each child with an intellectual disability, according to the individual differences between these children, and depending on the needs of each of them and their shortcomings and weaknesses, the importance of these programs stems from the inability of parents to provide a stimulating environment for their children to develop their abilities and skills in the presence of the natural environmental conditions surrounding them. In order for us to build any program on the basis of a sound scientific approach that has predetermined procedures and goals aimed at the success of the applied program, as without them there will be no basis for the program and thus it will not achieve its results. (John J. Shaughnessy & Eugene B. Zechmeister, 1997, p.8).

A planned and organized program was prepared that seeks to help intellectually disabled children develop clothing awareness according to a set of specific and organized steps that are based on theories that took into account children's learning, the researcher also took into account that the program works to take care of the child's capabilities, and the process of preparing the program went through the following steps:

- * The general planning of the program.
- * Determining the general and procedural objectives of the program.
- * Determine the program content.
- * Foundations for building the program.
- * Choose appropriate experiences activities.

The importance of the program

1. The program contributes to the development of clothing awareness among intellectually disabled children.

2. It is possible to benefit from the program proposed by workers in the field of special education, especially those working with intellectually disabled children.

General planning of the program:

The general planning process for the program includes defining the general and procedural goals and their practical and procedural content, such as the strategies and methods used in its implementation, determining the time span of the program, the number of activities and the location of the program, and then evaluating the program as a whole.

Foundations of building the program:

When preparing the program, the researcher took into account a set of principles:

- Taking into account the characteristics of children with intellectual disabilities.
- That the content of the program achieve its desired objectives.
- Use clear and understandable phrases and expressions for children.
- The activities presented should be interesting and enjoyable for children.
- Sequence of the activities presented so that the child can realize the goal of them.
- Dependence on the use of the senses in activities and games in order to fix the information in different ways.
- Diversity in the methods and techniques used in the games and program activities to suit individual differences between children.
- Continuing training on the program for a period of time sufficient for training.
- Not moving the child from one stage to another except after making sure of mastering the previous stage.
- Encouraging and supporting the child in all the actions he performs, proving and reinforcing him appropriately in case he performs what is required in a correct manner.
- Flexibility of dealing with children and establishing an atmosphere of familiarity between the researcher and children to ensure the continuity and success of the program.

Set general objectives for the program:**General objectives:**

1. Development of some concepts of clothing among intellectually disabled children.
2. Development of a healthy sense of color in intellectually disabled children.
3. The development of some concepts related to material in intellectually disabled children.
4. Development of design sense among intellectually disabled children.

Behavioral objectives:**The first axis (design)**

1. The girl can distinguish between different pieces of clothing: Dress / Blouse / Trouser / T-shirt.
2. The girl knows the types of neck holes.
3. The girl distinguished between the different lengths: long / short.
4. The girl knows the types and shapes of sleeves.
5. The girl knows the types and shapes of Al-Aqual.
6. The girl differentiates between the types of binders: zippers and buttons.
7. The girl knows the meaning of good control (Suitable design for the shape of the body).
8. The girl knows that the design is suitable for the place: school / home / outside the home.
9. The girl knows the appropriate styling for the occasion: Evening / Interview.
10. The girl knows the appropriate design for the time: winter / summer / evening / morning.
11. The girl chooses the appropriate accessory for her outfit.
12. The girl chooses the appropriate design by herself or with the help of the mother, sister or caregiver.

Second axis (color)

13. The girl knew the relationship of color to the surrounding environment.
14. The girl knows primary colors.
15. The girl knows monochrome.
16. The girl knows bilateral colors.
17. The girl knows tri-color.
18. The girl can create a set of colors from two colors.
19. The girl can distinguish between light and dark colors.
20. The girl can create a set of colors from three colors.
21. The girl knows the color gamut (light - medium - dark).
22. The girl differentiates the coloring methods: woody / watery / feltmaster.
23. The girl can use wooden pens.
24. The girl can use more than one method of coloring.

The third axis (material)

25. The girl associates heavy materials with cold weather, light materials and hot weather.
26. The girl differentiates between soft and rough materials.
27. The girl knows the types of fabrics: cotton / silk / wool.
28. The girl knows simple types of simple inscriptions.
29. The girl knows the embroidered materials.
30. The girl knows the types of melasma.
31. The girl can choose the appropriate material for the occasion.
32. The girl knows the meaning of the transparency of the material.
33. The girl knows how to choose the appropriate material for the design (T-shirt material - dress material).
34. The girl can distinguish raw materials in terms of their purchasing value (expensive / cheap).

Program preparation sources

In preparing the program, the researcher relied on several sources, including access to training, counseling and educational programs, previous studies, as well as the theoretical framework of the study, and what the researcher was able to read from Arab and foreign books and references on intellectually disabled children and children's programs, which contributed to the preparation of the program and the current study.

Determine the content of the program according to the characteristics of the growth and needs of children with intellectual disabilities:

Study procedures:

- The study sample and the size of the sample that can be handled were determined.
- Determine the appropriate time for activities.
- Determine appropriate reinforcement techniques for the child.
- Determining the most appropriate techniques for dealing with children.
- Knowing the difficulties that the researcher may face while implementing the program.
- The researcher adopted some methods of reinforcement in the program that are appropriate for children, namely:

A. Moral positive reinforcement techniques (with the words: bravo, smart, true).

B. Physical positive reinforcement techniques (candy, gifts, simple toys).

The appropriate strategies have been chosen in dealing with the children, and the researcher tried to diversify the strategies used in the program to take into account the principle of individual differences between children, and these strategies are:(Acting and role-playing, conceptual awareness strategy, dialogue and discussion, support, modeling).

Program arbitration

The researcher prepared the current study program in its final form according to the exploratory study, and then presented the program to (10) professors specializing in clothing, childhood, psychology, mental health, education and curricula.

Program arbitration result:

Among the most important proposals of the referees that the researcher followed was the following:

- Omitting some general objectives of the program.
- Arranging the program activities from the part to the whole, so that there are gradual educational situations.
- Determine the strategies and techniques used in each activity.

Amending the program according to the opinions of the referees and producing it in the final form to be applied to the children of the sample.

Table 3: The percentages of the arbitrators' agreement on the program

Arbitration items	The number of people who agree	Agreement percentage
The overall design of the program	10	%100
General objectives of the program	9	%90
Behavioral goals	8	%80
Program content and activities	8	%80

Procedural steps of the study

- In conducting the practical side of the current study, the researcher took the following steps:
- The study sample was selected from a category of intellectually disabled children, whose mental ages range from (6-9) years, and their IQ from (50-70).

- Conducting an interview with some of the male and female supervisors, to find out the extent of the intellectually disabled child perception of some of the dressing skills presented in the study, with the aim of preparing a questionnaire to measure the clothing awareness of intellectually disabled children, and with reference to the various measures, a questionnaire was constructed to measure the clothing awareness of intellectually disabled children.

- Preparing a program of activities based on daily life behavior to develop dress awareness among intellectually disabled children.

- Determine the study sample and homogenize it.

- Conducting a pre-measurement for the Mathematical Skills Scale for intellectually disabled children on the two study samples.

- Conducting the post questionnaire on the experimental sample.

- The researcher used the appropriate statistical methods and extracted the results of the study.

- The researcher interpreted the results of the study in light of the theoretical framework and previous studies.

Statistical methods used in the study:

Pearson correlation coefficient.

Wilcoxon equation.

Mann-Whitney test.

(Z)Value.

Results of the study and their interpretation:

The present study seeks to verify the following hypotheses:

The first hypothesis:

There is a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the experimental group scores in the pre-measurement and the post-measurement scale for developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills associated with clothing (design) in favor of post-measurement.

Table 4: The differences between the pre/ post measurements of the experimental group on the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends (design).

Experimental group	N	Average	Standard deviation	Degrees of freedom	Z value	Significance
pre-measurement	10	17.80	1.48	9	2.81	0.01
post-measurement		33.50	1.35			

It is evident from the previous table that the average ranks of the degrees of pre and post application and the standard deviation of the experimental group of the Scale of Developing Awareness of Clothing Trends and the daily life skills associated with clothing (design), as the average for the tribal application was (17.80), and the standard deviation was (1.48), and the mean post application for the same group was (33.50) degrees, and the standard deviation was (1.35) from a maximum degree (36), and this confirms the high awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (design) in favor of post application after implementing the program, and by calculating the Wilcoxon Test for the significance of the differences, it was found that the value of (Z) was (2.81) and it is a significant at the level of significance (0.01), and degrees of freedom (9), which fulfills the previous hypothesis, which is "there is a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the experimental group scores in the pre and post measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (design) in favor of post measurement."

These results are in agreement with the study of Jaber Issa (2012) on the effectiveness of a training program of some mathematical concepts (classification - sequence - Monosymmetry) in a sample of children with mild mental disabilities and comparing their performance with a group of normal children equivalent to them in mental age, and among the results of the study: Before implementing the program, there were differences in mathematical concepts between ordinary children and those with intellectual disabilities in favor of ordinary children despite the two groups being equal in mental age, and there are no differences between the two groups in concepts (classification - sequence - Monosymmetry) between the two groups who are normal and those with intellectual disabilities after applying the training program, and this confirms that children with intellectual disabilities can learn concepts like ordinary people who are equivalent to them in mental age, even if it requires more effort and time.

The second hypothesis

There is a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the experimental group scores in the pre-measurement and the post-measurement scale for developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills associated with clothing (color) in favor of post-measurement.

Table 5: Illustrates the differences between the pre/ post measurements of the experimental group on the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends (color)

Experimental group	N	Average	Standard deviation	Degrees of freedom	Z value	Significance
pre-measurement	10	21.40	1.51	9	2.82	0.01
post-measurement		34.70	0.675			

It is evident from the previous table that the average ranks of the pre and post application scores and the standard deviation of the experimental group for the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (color) and the average of the post application reached (21.40), and the standard deviation was (1.51), The average of post application for the same group was (34.70) degrees, and the standard deviation was (0.675) from a maximum score of (36). And this confirms the high awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (color) in favor of post application after implementing the program, and by calculating the Wilcoxon Test for the significance of the differences, it was found that the value of (Z) reached (2.81), which is significant at the level of significance (0.01), and degrees of freedom (9), which fulfills the previous hypothesis, which is "there is a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the experimental group scores in the pre and post measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (color) in favor of post measurement".

Among the studies that emphasized the importance of daily life experiences in learning concepts for children was the study of Legnard, Danielle; Austin, Susan (2014), and the study demonstrated the effect of the program's effectiveness and the development of mathematical concepts for children with simple intellectual disabilities. Through the previous presentation of the results of many previous studies, it is evident that any intervention in improving the educational environment for a child with an intellectual disability and the use of techniques, activities and educational programs codified for children with intellectual disabilities can improve their abilities as confirmed by the current study.

The third hypothesis

There is a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the experimental group scores in the pre/ post measurement of the Scale of Developing Awareness of Clothing Trends and Daily Living Skills related to clothing (material) in favor of post-measurement.

Table 6: The differences between the pre/ post measurements of the experimental group on the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends (material)

Experimental group	N	Average	Standard deviation	Degrees of freedom	Z value	Significance
pre-measurement	10	18.10	1.52	9	2.83	0.01
post-measurement		29.00	0.667			

It is evident from the previous table that the average ranks of the pre and post application scores and the standard deviation of the experimental group for the measure of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (material) as the average for the pre-application reached (18.10), and the standard deviation was (1.52), and the average of post application for the same group was (29.00) degrees, and the standard deviation was (0.667) from a maximum score (30).

This confirms the high awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (material) in favor of post application after implementing the program, and by calculating the Wilcoxon Test for the significance of the differences, it was found that the value of (Z) reached (2.83), which is significant at the level of significance (0.01), and (9) degrees of freedom, which fulfills the previous hypothesis, which is "there is a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the experimental group scores in the pre and post measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothes (material) in favor of post measurement".

This result can be interpreted and discussed in the light of the effectiveness and feasibility of the proposed program of activities for the development of clothing awareness and the techniques and experiences that were performed during the application period and this was agreed upon and confirmed by the study of Thurlow, Martha L. Turnure, James E. (2003) that the mathematical concepts that children with intellectual disabilities can learn are the concepts of time and money, through the study that was conducted on a sample of normal people and children with intellectual disabilities who are able to learn.

The fourth hypothesis

There is a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the experimental group scores in the pre/ post measurement scale for developing awareness of attitudes of clothing and daily life skills related to clothing (the scale as a whole) in favor of the post measurement.

Table 7: The differences between the pre/ post measurements of the experimental group on the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends (the scale as a whole)

Experimental group	N	Average	Standard deviation	Degrees of freedom	Z value	Significance
Pre-measurement	10	56.80	3.88	9	2.81	0.01
post-measurement		97.20	1.93			

It is evident from the previous table that the average ranks of the pre and post application scores and the standard deviation of the experimental group for the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (the scale as a whole), as the average for the pre-application was (56.80), and the standard deviation is (3.88), and the average of the post application for the same group is (97.20), and the standard deviation is (1.93) from a maximum score (102), and this confirms the high awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (scale as a whole) in favor of post application after implementing the program, and by calculating the Wilcoxon Test for the significance of the differences, it was found that the value of (Z) amounted to (2.81), which is a function of the level of significance (0.01), and (9) degrees of freedom and by calculating the Wilcoxon Test for the significance of the differences, it was found that the value of (Z) amounted to (2.81), which is significant of the level of significance (0.01), and (9) degrees of freedom. This achieves the previous hypothesis, which is "there is a statistically significant difference between the mean ranks of the experimental group scores in the pre and post measurement of the Scale of Developing Awareness of Clothing Trends and the daily life skills related to clothing (the scale as a whole) in favor of the post measurement".

The study of Diane M. Browder, Fred Spooner, Lynn Ahlgrim-Delzell, Amber A. Harris, Shawnee Wakemanxya (2008) identified systematic instructions for teaching mathematical skills to people with intellectual disabilities through experiments on 68 children with intellectual disabilities, and it turns out that number calculation, numbers matching and measurement have been learned through focusing on financial and monetary skills, which confirms daily life skills and their role in learning mathematical concepts.

The Fifth hypothesis:

There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the experimental group and the control group in the dimensional measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (design) for the benefit of the experimental group.

Table 8: The differences between the experimental and control groups in the dimensional measurement of the Scale of Developing Awareness of Clothing Trends (Design)

Experimental group	N	Average	Standard deviation	Degrees of freedom	Z value	Significance
Control	10	16.30	1.77	18	3.80	0.01
Experimental	10	33.5	1.35			

It is evident from the previous table that the average ranks of the post-application scores and the standard deviation of the experimental and control group for the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (design), where the average ranks of the post-application scores for the control group reached (16.30), and the standard deviation (1.77), the average scores for the post application of the experimental group was (33.5) degrees, and the standard deviation (1.35) of a maximum score (36), and this confirms the high awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (design) in favor of the experimental group after implementing the program, and by calculating the Mann-Whitney Test for the significance of differences, it was found that the value of (Z) reached (3.80), which is significant of the level of significance (0.01), and (18) degrees of freedom and this achieves the previous hypothesis, which is "there is a statistically significant difference between the average grades of the experimental group and the control group in the post measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (design) for the benefit of the experimental group.

The results of Amal Hassan's study (2013) also came in line with the results of the current study, as it aimed to investigate the extent to which the supermarket has been activated to develop some concepts and life-

mathematical skills in a kindergarten child as well as knowing the extent of the kindergarten child's ability to acquire life mathematical skills during his interaction in all the operations that take place within the supermarket (selling, buying, organizing goods on shelves, and methods of displaying goods).

The sixth hypothesis

There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the experimental and control group in the dimensional measurement of the scale of developing awareness of attitudes of clothing and daily life skills associated with clothing (color) in favor of the experimental group.

Table 9: The differences between the experimental and control group in the dimensional measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends (color)

Experimental group	N	Average	Standard deviation	Degrees of freedom	Z value	Significance
Control	10	19.70	1.83	18	3.84	0.01
Experimental	10	29.00	0.667			

It is evident from the previous table that the average ranks of the post-application scores and the standard deviation of the experimental and control group for the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (color), where the average ranks of the post-application scores for the control group was (19.70), and the standard deviation was (1.83) and the average ranks of the post application scores for the experimental group were (29.00) degrees, and the standard deviation was (0.667) from a maximum score (36), and this confirms the high awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (color) in favor of the experimental group after applying the program, and by calculating the Mann-Whitney Test for the significance of differences, it was found that the value of (Z) reached (3.84), which is significant at the level of significance (0.01).), and (18) degrees of freedom, and this achieves the previous hypothesis, which is "There is a statistically significant difference between the average grades of the experimental and control group in the post-measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (color) in favor of the experimental group.

The results of the current study are in agreement with the results of Marwa Suleiman's study (2007), which emphasized the importance of activities in the lives of ordinary kindergarten children and the hearing impaired. Through various activities, the personalities of these children can be constructed, and they can also learn indirectly through a program to impart some mathematical concepts to ordinary kindergarten children and the hearing impaired.

The seventh hypothesis

There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the experimental and control group in the dimensional measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (material) in favor of the experimental group.

Table 10: The differences between the experimental and control group in the post-measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends (material)

Experimental group	N	Average	Standard deviation	Degrees of freedom	Z value	Significance
Control	10	17.00	1.89	18	3.84	0.01
Experimental	10	29.00	0.667			

It is evident from the previous table that the average ranks of the post-application scores and the standard deviation of the experimental and control group for the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (material), where the average ranks of the post-application scores for the control group was (17.00), and the standard deviation was (1.89), and the average ranks of the post application scores for the experimental group were (29.00) degrees, and the standard deviation was (0.667) from a maximum score (30).

This confirms the high awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (material) in favor of the experimental group after applying the program, and by calculating the Mann-Whitney Test for the significance of differences, it was found that the value of (Z) reached (3.84), which is significant at the level of significance (0.01), and (18) degrees of freedom, and this achieves the previous hypothesis, which is "there is a statistically significant difference between the average grades of the experimental and control group in the post-

measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothes (material) for the benefit of the experimental group.

The study of Diane M. Browder, Fred Spooner, Lynn Ahlgrim-Delzell, Amber A. Harris, Shawnee Wakemanxya (2008) identified systematic instructions for teaching mathematical skills to people with intellectual disabilities through experiments on 68 children with intellectual disabilities, and it turns out that number calculation, numbers matching and measurement have been learned through focusing on financial and monetary skills, which confirms daily life skills and their role in learning mathematical concepts.

The eighth hypothesis

There is a statistically significant difference between the mean scores of the experimental and control group in the dimensional measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (the scale as a whole) in favor of the experimental group.

Table 11: The differences between the experimental and control group in the post-measurement of the Scale of Developing Awareness of Clothing Trends (the scale as a whole)

Experimental group	N	Average	Standard deviation	Degrees of freedom	Z value	Significance
Control	10	53.00	4.78	18	3.79	0.01
Experimental	10	97.20	1.93			

It is evident from the previous table that the average ranks of the post-application scores and the standard deviation of the experimental and control group for the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (the scale as a whole), where the average ranks of the post-application scores for the control group reached (53.00), and standard deviation (4.78), and the average ranks of the post application scores for the experimental group reached (97.20), and the standard deviation was (1.93) from a maximum score (102), and this confirms the high awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (the scale as a whole) in favor of the experimental group after implementing the program, and by calculating the Mann-Whitney Test for the significance of differences, it was found that the value of (Z) reached (3.79), which is significant at the level of significance (0.01), and (18) degrees of freedom. This achieves the previous hypothesis, which is “there is a statistically significant difference between the average grades of the experimental group and the control group in the post-measurement of the scale of developing awareness of clothing trends and daily life skills related to clothing (the scale as a whole) in favor of the experimental group.

The results of the current study are in agreement with the results of Marwa Suleiman’s study (2007), which emphasized the importance of activities in the lives of ordinary kindergarten children and the hearing impaired. Through various activities, the personalities of these children can be built, and they can also learn indirectly through a program to impart some mathematical concepts to ordinary kindergarten children and the hearing impaired.

Recommendations and Suggestions

1. In light of the results of the current study, the following recommendations and proposals can be drawn up:
2. Instructing teachers using techniques and strategies, including taking advantage of the different environments “home environment - school environment” to develop concepts among children with special needs.
3. Choosing appropriate programs for this group and stage of age, according to their characteristics, in order to provide programs aimed at the integration of the child with his companions and their participation in various other activities.
4. That a teacher or teacher with special needs is aware of the cognitive and psychological characteristics of children of this stage, and it is preferable that the teacher of special groups for this age group holds a Bachelor of Education (kindergarten) specializing in special classes.
5. Training parents on appropriate educational programs for their children, each according to his disability.
6. The programs and applied activities for the kindergarten sector at the Ministry of Education are presented periodically and continuously.

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Author Information

Dr. Ilham Fathy AbdelAziz

Associate Professor of Fashion Design and Modeling
on Mannequin, Department of Garment and Textile -
King Abdul-Aziz University
